

IPIN 2017

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Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning (PDR) Tutorial

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POLITÉCNICA

Outline

- Some theory:

1. What is PDR?
2. Inertial Navigation (INS)
3. Implementation problems
4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- Practice (Matlab):

1. Introduction
2. PDR with pre-recorded logfiles
3. PDR with your own phone

- Evaluation (Kahoot)

What is PDR?

- A method to:
 - **estimate the user's trajectory** (Position & Heading)
 - by **integrating inertial measurements**
- No need of external beacons: GPS, Cell-positioning, LPS (WiFi, BLE, UWB, US, Light,...)
- Assumes known initial conditions:
 - position and orientation
- Uses Inertial data:
 - Acceleration (m/s^2)
 - Angular rate (rad/s)

What is PDR?

- «Acceleration & Angular rate» signals to integrate
 - Example: 60 meters walk
 - go (18 steps) + 180° turn (1 step) + return walk (18 steps)

What is PDR?

- Acceleration, Angular rate, trajectory integration ... it sounds like «Inertial Navigation» or INS...

↓ INS

- Can I use inertial navigation syst. (INS) for PDR?

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2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- INS

- Uses an **IMU** (Inertial Measurement Unit)

- 3 accelerometers (measuring “specific force” [m/s²] caused by **motion** and also **gravity**)
- 3 gyroscopes (measure “angular rate” [rad/s])

- Applies navigation equations integrating Inertial data

- Starting from an initial position and pose, estimates the final trajectory of a moving object

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- Global Reference frame (**n-frame** of navigation) :
 - Inertial (Earth Centered), ECEF, Local (Leveled)
- Attitude:
 - 3D orientation of body IMU reference system (**b-frame**) respect to the global reference system (**n-frame**)
 - Euler: Roll, Pitch, Yaw,
 - Direction Cosine Matrix (DCM): R_b^n ,
 - Quaternions, etc

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- Attitude example (Euler):
 - 3 independent rotations around:
 - X(Roll) -> Y(Pitch) -> Z (Yaw)

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- 2 types of INS:
 - 1) **INS with stabilized platform (Gimbal)**
 - Stabilized with motors to keep gyro signals to zero.
 - Readings of axis: (Roll,Pitch,Yaw) directly gives the Attitude
 - Accelerometer signals are in n-frame => so INS only has to subtract “gravity”, and double integration to get V and P

Gimbal frame

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- 2) Strap-down INS:

- No stabilized platform. 3 Acc y 3Gyr fixed to the body.
- Integrate angular rate (Gyro) to keep track of Attitude (R_b^n)
- Transform specific force (f^b) measured by accelerometers in b-frame to n-frame (f^n) using Attitude.
- Eliminate gravity (g) to that acceleration (f^n), obtaining: f'^n
- Integrate f'^n to obtain velocity (V^n), and again to get position (P^n)

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- Strap-down INS: Implementation in Matlab

```

%-----
% INS
% Acc: IMU Acelerometer signal (3 axis) [m/s^2]
% Gyr: IMU Angular Rate signal (3 axis) [rad/s]
% fs: Frecuencia muestreo [Hz]

```



```

% Actualizar matriz de orientación con valores de los "Gyros"
SkewGyros=[0 -Gyr(i,3) Gyr(i,2);...
           Gyr(i,3) 0 -Gyr(i,1);...
           -Gyr(i,2) Gyr(i,1) 0]*pi/180; % rad/s
Rot_nb(:, :, i)=Rot_nb(:, :, i-1)*(2*eye(3)+SkewGyros/fs)*inv(2*eye(3)-SkewGyros/fs); % Pade(1,1)

```

2. Inertial Navigation (INS)

- INS concept is easy and we have the code
- So, PDR problem is solved:
 - Let's take an IMU and
 - implement PDR as INS !!!
- Any problem with that?
 - Yes, several....

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3. Implementation problems

- The size and weight of IMU:
 - Pure INS solutions require bulky sensors
 - Not good to be carried by a person in PDR

MEMS

3. Implementation problems

- The noise in the MEMS IMU:
 - Additive noise in Acc & Gyr readings
 - Bias (systematic, unstability, turn on)
 - Orthogonality, scaling, thermal
- Noise generates:
 - Integration errors
 - Errors in Attitude

Xsens Mti:

Acc	Acceleration Range (g)	VRW ($\mu g/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$)	BRW (mg)
	$\pm 5/18$	122	0.05
Gyr	Angular Rate Range ($^{\circ}/s$)	ARW ($^{\circ}/\sqrt{\text{hr}}$)	BRW ($^{\circ}/\text{hr}$)
	± 300	3	50

Static accuracy (roll/pitch)	<0.5 deg
Static accuracy (heading) ¹	<1 deg
Dynamic accuracy	2 deg RMS
Angular resolution	0.05 deg

¹ in homogeneous magnetic environment

3. Implementation problems

Attitude error => gravity to leak as acceleration

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 - ➔ 4. PDR algorithmic solutions
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4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- Ways to improve INS for Pedestrians:
 - 1) Split the INS problem into pieces: Step by step

- 2) Apply human motion models:
 - Step frequency: 1Hz (useful for signal filtering and stance length estimation),
 - Foot on floor (if IMU at foot => Velocity=0 at stance; ZUPT)

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- Walking Phases:
 - 2 states (stance and swing) and 7 different phases
 - The stance (60%) and swing (40%) phases
 - For a foot-mounted IMU: Magnitude of Acc & Gyr are stable during Midstance (central stance phase)

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- Foot-attached IMU signals at stance:

IMU signals at foot stance

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- There are **2 main types of PDR** algorithms:
 - **“INS-ZUPT”**: Integrates accelerations (INS) and correct velocities with **zero velocity** updates (ZUPT) at **stance**. **IMU** must be on **foot**.
 - **“SL+ θ ”**: Accumulates **Stride Length (SL)** estimations, along the **Orientation angle (θ)** at foot **stance**. **General purpose (IMU anywhere)**

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- General block diagram for an IMU-based Pedestrian Navigation System:

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- Step detection

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- **Step detection** using Accelerometers:

1

Magnitude of acceleration

$$a_i = \sqrt{a_{x_i}^2 + a_{y_i}^2 + a_{z_i}^2}$$

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- **Step Length (SL) Weinberg Algorithm.**

- Assumes SL is prop. to BOUNCE (vertical movement of hip)
- Bounce estimated from largest Acc.

1

Magnitude of acceleration

$$a_i = \sqrt{a_{x_i}^2 + a_{y_i}^2 + a_{z_i}^2}$$

2

Low-Pass Filter

$$\tilde{a}_i = LP(a_i)$$

3

Weinberg hip bounce model

$$SL_{\text{Weinberg}_k} = K \cdot \left\{ \max_{j=[i_{(k)} \pm w]} \tilde{a}_j - \min_{j=[i_{(k)} \pm w]} \tilde{a}_j \right\}^{1/4}$$

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- **Attitude estimation (AHRS):**

- Orientation from gyroscopes (relative) :

$$\omega^s = (\omega_x^s, \omega_y^s, \omega_z^s) \quad \text{Gyro signals}$$

$$C(t) = C(0) \cdot \exp\left(\int_0^t \Omega(\tau) d\tau\right)$$

C (rotation matrix) computed integrating the skew symmetric matrix from an initial orientation

- Orientation from accelerometers and magnetometer (absolute references):

$$m^s = (m_x^s, m_y^s, m_z^s) \quad \text{magnetometer signals}$$

$$a^s = (a_x^s, a_y^s, a_z^s) \quad \text{acceleration signals}$$

- Some Integrated AHRS algorithms (optimal weighting):

- Madwick AHRS algorithm (Gradient descent optimization gyro vs. accel/magne).
 - Mahony AHRS algorithm (complementary filter)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \phi = \tan\left(\frac{a_y^s}{a_z^s}\right)^{-1} \quad \text{Pitch} \\ \theta = \tan\left(\frac{-a_x^s}{\sqrt{(a_y^s)^2 + (a_z^s)^2}}\right)^{-1} \quad \text{Roll} \\ \psi = \tan\left(\frac{-m_x^h}{m_y^h}\right)^{-1} \pm D \quad \text{Yaw} \end{array} \right.$$

$$q_{fused}(k) = \gamma \cdot q_g(k) + (1 - \gamma) \cdot q_{a/m}(k)$$

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- **PDR Algorithm: “SL+ θ ”:**

- The SL can be computed, e.g.:

$$SL_{\text{Weiberg}_k} = K \cdot \left\{ \max_{j=[i_{(k)} \pm w]} \tilde{a}_j - \min_{j=[i_{(k)} \pm w]} \tilde{a}_j \right\}^{1/4}$$

- The θ angle at foot stance, computed using gyros (& opt. magnetometers).
- Accumulates Stride Length (SL) estimations along the Orientation (θ)

$$\begin{cases} P_k(\text{north}) = P_{k-1}(\text{north}) + SL_k \cdot \cos(\theta_{\text{stance}_k}) \\ P_k(\text{east}) = P_{k-1}(\text{east}) + SL_k \cdot \sin(\theta_{\text{stance}_k}), \end{cases}$$

- “K” number of steps
- Method valid con “normal” walking (only forward walk).

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- PDR Algorithm: **“INS-ZUPT”** :

- Integrate accelerations to obtain velocity (INS).

- Correct velocity at foot stance (ZUPT).

Correct v_i^G

3a Mean velocity stance k

$$\mu_k = \sum_{j=i(k)-w}^{s(k)+w} v_j^G / (2w + 1)$$

3b Correct all samples in step by interpolation

$$\check{v}_i^G = v_i^G - [\mu_k(i - i_{(k-1)}) + \mu_{k-1}(i_{(k)} - i)] / m_k.$$

4. PDR algorithmic solutions

- PDR Algorithm: “INS-ZUPT” (cont):

- Accumulates position increments:

$$\Delta P_i = \check{v}_i^G \cdot \Delta T$$

$$\begin{cases} P_i(\text{north}) = P_{i-1}(\text{north}) + \Delta P_i(\text{north}) \\ P_i(\text{east}) = P_{i-1}(\text{east}) + \Delta P_i(\text{east}). \end{cases}$$

- Method valid for “any” type of walk (forward/lateral/backwards walk, running, crawling, etc).
- ...but IMU must be on foot

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Practice: Introduction

- Requirements for practice:

- **Laptop computer** (any O.S. valid: Mac / Linux / Windows).

- **Octave** software (or **Matlab**) should be installed in your computer. Octave is freely available at:

<https://www.gnu.org/software/octave/download.html>

Download

The latest stable version is GNU Octave 4.2.1:

- [octave-4.2.1-w32-installer.exe](#) (~ 170 MB) [signature]
- [octave-4.2.1-w64-installer.exe](#) (~ 184 MB) [signature]
- [octave-4.2.1-w32.zip](#) (~ 280 MB) [signature]
- [octave-4.2.1-w64.zip](#) (~ 378 MB) [signature]

All Windows binaries with corresponding source code can be downloaded from <https://ftp.gnu.org/ftp.gnu.com/pub/gnu/octave/windows/>

- A **smartphone** with **Android** operating system is needed for one of the practices. The "**GetSensorData.apk**" app should be installed.

App available at "Lopsi > More>Downloads":

<http://lopsi.weebly.com/downloads.html>

Log_files in your phone => transferred to your computer via USB cable, Bluetooth, e-mail,...

Downloads

Available downloads:

1) App for recording all sensors readings in a smartphone

The "GetSensorData" app (for Android) is capable of recording into a logfile all the sensor information available recording WiFi RSS, Inertial data (Accelerometer and Gyroscope), Magnetic, GPS, the orientation of the phone, Humidity, Sound intensity and Light intensity.

This is the app used for the International IPIN 2016 Competition (track 3). It is also planned to be used in future to make your own experimentation for further signal processing and location estimation. Next, some pictures

 [getsensordata.apk](#)
Download File

 [getsensordata20.apk](#)
Download File

- If not => you must integrate into a team

Practice: Introduction

- Download PDR Octave/Matlab software:

The screenshot shows a web browser window at the URL `lopsi.weebly.com/teaching.html`. The page header includes logos for the Spanish Government, the Ministry of Science and Innovation, and the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), along with the 'LOPSI' logo and a contact menu. The navigation menu includes 'HOME', 'RESEARCH', 'PROJECTS', 'PUBLICATIONS', 'VIDEOS', 'MORE', and 'CONTACT'. A dropdown menu is open under 'MORE', showing 'Teaching', 'Downloads', and 'Start-Up'. A blue arrow points from a green callout box 'Lopsi > More > Teaching' to the 'Teaching' option in the dropdown. Below the navigation, the page is titled 'Ph.D. Teaching' and describes master/doctorate classes at the University of Alcalá de Henares. A list of topics is provided, including 'Tema 3.3: Sistemas de localización en interiores basados en radiofrecuencia' and 'Tema 4: Sistemas de posicionamiento en exteriores'. Under the 'Tutorials' section, there is a text block: 'We teach a Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning Tutorial. You can download the PDR Tutorial powerpoint slides here and the Matlab code to do the practice here.' Two download links are shown: 'tutorial_pdr.zip Download File' and 'pedestrian_dead-reckoning__pdr__tutorial.pdf Download File'. A blue arrow points from a green callout box 'Download PDR SW' to the first download link. Another blue arrow points from a green callout box 'PDR Tutorial slides' to the second download link.

Lopsi > More > Teaching

Download PDR SW

PDR Tutorial slides

Practice: Introduction

- **Matlab algorithms and logfiles:**

- Three main files, for 3 practices

- PDR algorithms:

- INS for position & Attitude
- Step detection
- Step length estimation
- Two PDR types:
 - INS-ZUPT,
 - SL+theta

- Tools:

- Visualization and
- Log_file interpretation

- Log_files:

- #1 ideal (4 loops),
- #2 rectangular (3 loops) with 2 different IMUs
- You will create your own log_files

Name	Size	Date Modified	Type
main_P3.m	2 KB	31/01/17 12:32	MATLAB Scrip
main_P2.m	3 KB	31/01/17 12:58	MATLAB Scrip
main_P1.m	2 KB	31/01/17 15:34	MATLAB Scrip
ZUPT_StrideLength_Heading_Position.m	9 KB	30/01/17 16:37	MATLAB Fun..
Weiberg_StrideLength_Heading_Position.m	5 KB	30/01/17 16:30	MATLAB Fun..
visualizar_INS_results.m	3 KB	26/01/17 12:27	MATLAB Fun..
StepDetection_Gyro.m	3 KB	2/11/09 13:36	MATLAB Fun..
StepDetection_Acel_smartphone.m	3 KB	30/01/17 16:00	MATLAB Fun..
StepDetection_Acel.m	4 KB	27/01/17 17:40	MATLAB Fun..
ReadLogFile.m	25 KB	30/01/17 15:51	MATLAB Fun..
INS.m	6 KB	31/01/17 15:34	MATLAB Fun..
log_files		31/01/17 15:50	File Folder
logfile_3loops_forward.txt	8 MB	25/01/17 13:26	Documento ...
logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt	8 MB	25/01/17 13:31	Documento ...
ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.txt	4 MB	24/01/17 12:12	Documento ...
logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.mat	3 MB	31/01/17 13:08	MAT File
ideal_footIMU_rectangulo_GT.mat	892 KB	24/01/17 12:12	MAT File
ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.mat	474 KB	31/01/17 15:34	MAT File

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PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS

- Using a synthetic logfile:

- Simulated IMU:

- acceleration (Acc), turn rates (Gyr) and magnetic field (Mag)

- Ground-truth included (4 loops):

- position (Pos), velocity (Vel) and orientation (Euler and DCM)

- Units are in:

- meters, seconds and radians.

- Sampling frequency: 100 Hz

- IMU rotated on foot as in picture.

- All trajectories starts at point (0,0,0)

- Gravity is 9.8 m/s²

- Study INS results for noiseless and noise cases

1.2) Closed trajectory in a square loop of 30 x 30 m.

[Download dataset](#)

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS

```
% -----  
%      PDR Tutorial: PRACTICE 1 (main_P1.m)  
%      Lopsi Group. CAR-CSIC/UPM  
%      2017  
% -----  
clc; clear all; close all; disp('PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS');  
%      PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS  
% 1) Load ideal noise-free data (ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.txt) and inspect  
% 2) Apply INS algorithm (INS.m) to ideal IMU signals and check correct integration  
% 3) Add noise (rand or bias) to IMU signals and inspect drift in velocity and position generated
```


PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

• PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS

```
%.....  
% 1) Load ideal noise-free data (ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.txt) and inspect  
  
% Read log_file  
disp('1) Load ideal noise-free data (ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.txt) and inspect');  
disp('Reading Logfile...');  
[~,~,Acc,Gyr]=ReadLogFile('..\log_files\ideal_footIMU_rectangulo.txt','Xsens'); % load IMU simulated data: f  
load('..\log_files\ideal_footIMU_rectangulo_GT.mat'); % load Ground_truth data: 'Pos_G','Vel_G','Att_G','Rot_  
disp('Logfile Read...');  
disp('-> TO DO: Inspect IMU signals (press enter to continue)');  
pause;  
  
%.....  
% 2) Apply INS algorithm (INS.m) to ideal IMU signals and check correct integration  
disp(sprintf('\n2) Apply INS algorithm (INS.m) to ideal IMU signals and check correct integration'));  
% Apply INS to obtain Pos,Vel y Att:  
disp('Applying INS...');  
[Pos_G_rec,Vel_G_rec,Att_G_rec]=INS(Acc,Gyr);  
disp('INS ended. Showing results...');  
visualizar_INS_results(Pos_G_rec,Vel_G_rec,Att_G_rec,Pos_G,Vel_G,Att_G,Rot_GS,Stance,StepDectSample,10);  
disp('-> TO DO: Check correct integration (press enter to continue)');  
pause;
```


PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

• PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS

```
%.....  
% 3) Add noise (rand or bias) to IMU signals and inspect drift  
disp(sprintf('\n3) Add noise (rand or bias) to IMU signals and inspect drift'));  
Amplitud=0.0; % m/s^2  
Bias=0.0; % m/s^2  
samples=length(Acc);  
Acc(:,1:3)=Acc(:,1:3)+Amplitud*randn(samples,3);  
Acc(:,3)=Acc(:,3)+Bias*ones(samples,1);  
  
Amplitud=0.0; % rad/s  
Bias=0.001; % rad/s  
samples=length(Gyr);  
Gyr(:,1:3)=Gyr(:,1:3)+Amplitud*randn(samples,3);  
Gyr(:,3)=Gyr(:,3)+Bias*ones(samples,1);  
  
% Apply INS to obtain Pos, Vel y Att:  
disp('Applying INS with noise...');  
[Pos_G_rec, Vel_G_rec, Att_G_rec]=INS(Acc, Gyr);  
disp('INS with noise ended. Showing results...');  
visualizar_INS_results(Pos_G_rec, Vel_G_rec, Att_G_rec, Pos_G, Vel_G, Att_G, Rot_GS, Stance, StepDectSample, 20);  
disp('-> TO DO: Check correct integration (press enter to continue)');
```


PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 1: Effects of noise on INS

- **Conclusions:**

- INS works perfectly on ideal or noiseless IMU data
- INS does not work if sensor data has:
 - Bias, Noise,
 - Low sampling frequency
 - Quantization, saturated
 - Axis misalignments

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsens-MEMS IMU

- One square 3 times (76 steps: 22+23+31, forward walk, but last 3 sides lateral/backwards walk)

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsens-MEMS IMU

```
§ -----  
§      PDR Tutorial: PRACTICE 2 (main_P2.m)  
§      Lopsi Group. CAR-CSIC/UPM  
§      2017  
§ -----  
  
clc; clear all; close all; disp('PRACTICE 2: PDR with FOOT-MOUNTED real XSENS-MEMS IMU');  
§  
§      PRACTICE 2: PDR with FOOT-MOUNTED real XSENS-MEMS IMU  
§ 1) Load real data with foot-mounted IMU (logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt)  
§      -One square 3 times (76: 22+23+31 steps, forward walk, but last 3 sides lateral/backwards walk)  
§ 2) Apply INS PDR algorithm and analyse drifts in position  
§ 3) Apply INS-ZUPT and analyse processing:  
§      -Detection of steps and stance  
§      -Correction of Velocities to zero (ZUPT)  
§      -Walking direction
```

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsens-MEMS IMU

```
% .....  
% 1) Load real data with foot-mounted IMU (logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt)  
%     -One square 3 times (76: 22+23+31 steps, forward walk, but last 3 sides lateral/backwards walk)  
  
% Read log_file  
disp('1) Load real data with foot-mounted test and inspect');  
disp('Reading Logfile...');  
% load IMU read data: Acc,Gyr de Xsens (3 loops)  
[~,~,Acc,Gyr]=ReadLogFile('.\log_files\logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt','Xsens',1); % 76 steps (2 loops  
% [~,~,Acc,Gyr]=ReadLogFile('.\log_files\logfile_3loops_forward.txt','Xsens',1); % 66 steps (3 loops)  
disp('Logfile Read...');  
disp('-> TO DO: Inspect IMU signals and bias (press enter to continue)');  
pause;
```

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsens-MEMS IMU

```
%.....  
% 2) Apply INS PDR algorithm and analyse drifts in position (remove bias)  
disp(sprintf('\n2) Apply INS PDR algorithm and analyse drifts in position (remove bias)'));  
% Remove bias Gyro  
samples=5000; % asumo 50 segundos parado (y fs=100 Hz)  
bias_Gyr=[mean(Gyr(1:samples,1)), mean(Gyr(1:samples,2)), mean(Gyr(1:samples,3))];  
Gyr_unbiased=Gyr; % [nx4]  
Gyr_unbiased(:,1:3)=[Gyr(:,1)-bias_Gyr(1), Gyr(:,2)-bias_Gyr(2), Gyr(:,3)-bias_Gyr(3)];  
  
% Apply INS to obtain Pos, Vel y Att:  
disp('Applying INS...');  
[Pos_G_rec, Vel_G_rec, Att_G_rec]=INS(Acc, Gyr);  
% [Pos_G_rec, Vel_G_rec, Att_G_rec]=INS(Acc, Gyr_unbiased);  
disp('INS ended. Showing results...');  
idx_fig=10;  
visualizar_INS_results(Pos_G_rec, Vel_G_rec, Att_G_rec, idx_fig);  
disp('-> TO DO: Check uncorrect INS integration/ remove bias (press enter to continue)');  
pause;
```

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsens-MEMS IMU

76 steps should be detected

```

%.....
% 3) Apply INS-ZUPT and analyse processing:
%     -Detection of steps and stance
%     -Correction of Velocities to zero (ZUPT)
%     -Walking direction

```

```

disp(sprintf('\n3) Apply INS-ZUPT and analyse processing'));
disp('Applying INS-ZUPT...');
%-----Step detection-----
idx_fig=20;
[Num_steps,Step_events,StancePhase,idx_fig]=StepDetection_Acel(Acc,1,idx_fig);
%-----INS-ZUPT-----
[StrideLengths,Thetas,Positions,idx_fig]=ZUPT_StrideLength_Heading_Position(Acc,Gyr,Step_events,StancePhase,1,idx_fig);
%|[StrideLengths,Thetas,Positions,idx_fig]=ZUPT_StrideLength_Heading_Position(Acc,Gyr_unbiased,Step_events,StancePhase,1,idx_fig);

disp('INS-ZUPT ended. Showing results...');
disp('-> TO DO: Check correct integration INS-ZUPT');

```


Check: Step detection thresholds

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

- PRACTICE 2: PDR with foot-mounted real Xsen-MEMS IMU

- **Conclusions:**

- Bias&noise in Gyros cause attitude errors growing linear with time => big problems
- INS does not work with MEMS IMUs, even with bias removed
- INS-ZUPT makes PDR, with bias removed, to work pretty well (for foot-mounted IMU)

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

• PRACTICE 3: PDR with hand-held real smartphone IMU (Samsung S4)

```
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# PDR Tutorial: PRACTICE 3 (mai_P3.m)  
# Lopsi Group. CAR-CSIC/UPM  
# 2017  
#-----
```

```
clc; clear all; close all; disp('PRACTICE 3: PDR with hand-held real smartphone IMU (Samsung S4) ');  
#  
# PRACTICE 3: PDR with hand-held real smartphone IMU (Samsung S4)  
# 1) Load real data with smart-phone IMU (logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt)  
# -One square 3x (76 steps, forward walk, but last 3 sides lateral/backwards walk)  
# 2) Apply SL+theta PDR algorithm and analyse results:  
# -Check bias remove effect  
# -Step detection & Stride Length estimation  
# -Position estimation while walking lateral/backwards  
#  
#.....  
# 1) Load real data with smart-phone IMU (logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt)  
# -One square 3 times (76 steps, forward walk, but last 3 sides lateral/backwards walk)  
#  
# Read log_file  
disp('1) Load real data with smart-phone IMU and inspect');  
disp('Reading Logfile...');  
# load IMU read data: Acc,Gyr de Xsens (3 loops)  
#[~,~,Acc,Gyr]=ReadLogFile('..\log_files\logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt','Xsens',1); %ON FOOT % (2 loops + 1 )  
[Acc,Gyr,~,~]=ReadLogFile('..\log_files\logfile_3loops_1lateralbackwards.txt','smartphone',1); %ON HAND % (2 loops +  
disp('Logfile Read...');
```


PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

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%.....  
% 2) Apply SL+theta PDR algorithm and analyse results  
%     -Check bias remove effect  
%     -Step detection & Stride Length estimation  
%     -Position estimation while walking lateral/backwards  
disp(sprintf('\n2) Apply SL+theta PDR algorithm and analyse results'));  
% Remove bias Gyro  
samples=5000; % asumo 50 segundos parado (y fs=100 Hz)  
bias_Gyr=[mean(Gyr(1:samples,1)), mean(Gyr(1:samples,2)), mean(Gyr(1:samples,3))];  
Gyr_unbiased=Gyr; % [nx4]  
Gyr_unbiased(:,1:3)=[Gyr(:,1)-bias_Gyr(1), Gyr(:,2)-bias_Gyr(2), Gyr(:,3)-bias_Gyr(3)];  
  
% Apply INS to obtain Pos, Vel y Att:  
disp('Apply SL+theta PDR...');  
%-----Step detection-----  
idx_fig=20;  
%[Num_steps, Step_events, StancePhase, idx_fig]=StepDetection_Acel(Acc,1,idx_fig);  
[Num_steps, Step_events, StancePhase, idx_fig]=StepDetection_Acel_smartphone(Acc,1,idx_fig);  
%-----SL-theta-----  
%[StrideLengths, Thetas, Positions, idx_fig]=Weiberg_StrideLength_Heading_Position(Acc,Gyr, Step_events, StancePhase, :);  
[StrideLengths, Thetas, Positions, idx_fig]=Weiberg_StrideLength_Heading_Position(Acc,Gyr_unbiased, Step_events, StancePhase, :);
```

PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

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PDR with pre-recorded logfiles

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- Conclusions:

- Step detection is more challenging
- SL+theta PDR is good for forward walking, but can be cheated if direction of motion and direction of IMU/phone is not the same
- Still to be done: create a robust PDR method for free phone position vs person's motion

Outline

- Some theory:
 1. What is PDR?
 2. Inertial Navigation (INS)
 3. Implementation problems
 4. PDR algorithmic solutions
- Practice (Matlab):
 1. Introduction
 2. PDR with pre-recorded logfiles
 3. PDR with your own phone
- Evaluation (Kahoot)

PDR with your own phone

- PRACTICE 4: SL+ θ PDR with your phone

– Now is when you need:

1. Your Android phone
2. App «**GetSensorData**».

Download App from:

<http://lopsi.weebly.com/downloads.html>

– If not such a phone & App => Team

A screenshot of the 'GetSensorData' app interface. The app has a dark header with the title 'GetSensorData' and a menu icon. Below the header are three buttons: 'Show Sensor Features', 'Hide Real-time Data', and 'Start Saving a Log File'. The main content area lists several sensors with their current values and update frequencies. The sensors listed are: ACCE: LSM330DLC Acceleration Sensor (Acc(X): 0.36285 m/s^2, Acc(Y): 5.08965 m/s^2, Acc(Z): 8.27681 m/s^2, Freq: 50 Hz); GYRO: LSM330DLC Gyroscope Sensor (Gyr(X): -0.03451 rad/s, Gyr(Y): 0.24587 rad/s, Gyr(Z): -0.01222 rad/s, Freq: 217 Hz); MAGN: AK8975C Magnetic field Sensor (Mag(X): 12.31250 uT, Mag(Y): -22.50000 uT, Mag(Z): -20.18750 uT, Freq: 99 Hz); PRES: LPS331AP Pressure sensor (Pressure: 951.32 mbar, Freq: 25 Hz); LIGH: CM36651 Light Sensor (Light Intensity: 494.0 Lux, Freq: 50 Hz); PROX: CM36651 Proximity Sensor (Proximity: 6.0 Units, Freq: 0 Hz). At the bottom, there is a red bar with the text 'No IMU. All sensors are connected' and a button labeled 'Mark First Position'.

PDR with your own phone

• PRACTICE 4: SL+ θ PDR with your phone

– Tasks to be done:

- Design a trajectory of your wish (control number of steps, turns, ending position,..)
- Remember to keep **phone in front of you**
- **Start recording** with the App (Start button)
- Initial **50 sec still** (easy Gyro bias removal)
- Move along planned trajectory. Pres Stop button.
- Transfer recorded logfile to your PC
- Apply the **SL+ θ PDR** algorithm (main_P3.m)
- Analyze results by teams (repeat test if necessary). Ask any question...

Start Button

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 Evaluation (Kahoot)

Testing PDR with Kahoot

- [Play PDR evaluation game:](#)

The image shows the Kahoot! interface for a game titled "Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning - PDR Tutorial". The background is purple. At the top, the Kahoot! logo is displayed in white. Below the logo, the game title is shown in a white box. There are two main options for playing the game, each with an icon of a hand holding a smartphone and a corresponding button below it.

Kahoot!

Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning - PDR Tutorial

Player vs Player
1:1 Devices
Classic

Team vs Team
Shared Devices
Team mode

You must visit this web page:

<https://kahoot.it/>

Some PDR references

- Oliver J. Woodman, “**An introduction to inertial navigation**”, UCAM-CL-TR-696, 2007.
- R. Harle. “**A survey of indoor inertial positioning systems for pedestrians**”. IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials, 15(3), pp. 1281-1293, 2013.
- Skog et al, “**Zero-velocity detection in pedestrian navigation systems - an algorithm evaluation,**” Biomedical Engineering, vol. 57, no. 11, pp. 2657–2666, 2010.
- A.R. Jiménez et al., «**A Comparison of Pedestrian Dead-Reckoning Algorithms using a Low-Cost MEMS IMU**», WISP, pp. 37-42, 2009.

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ありがとう

Arigatō

Thank you

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